

CREATION AND MAINTENANCE OF STATE CADASTERS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: This article contains information about the creation and maintenance of state cadastres in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the concept of state cadastre and its content, the unified system of state cadastres, the accounting of cadastral objects, cadastral documents, cadastral volumes and cadastral maps.

Keywords: cadastre, map, ArcGIS, database, resource, building, structure, collection.

INTRODUCTION

Taking into account the development of economic reforms carried out in all sectors of the national economy, the rational use of natural and economic resources and the improvement of the management system for their protection, as well as the comprehensive analysis and assessment of the natural and economic potential of the regions, are considered one of the most necessary issues.

The cadastral system, which is one of the main elements of the market economy, fully complies with the main principles and content of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Today, it plays an important role in deepening the reforms in the economic spheres.

The methodology, scientific principles and concepts of creating and maintaining state cadastres are determined by the responsible ministries, state committees and agencies that maintain state cadastres.

State cadastre of occurrences of land, mines, minerals and man-made products in our republic; state water cadastre; state forest cadastre; state cadastre of protected natural areas; state cadastre of buildings and structures; state cadastre of hydrotechnical facilities; state cadastre of cultural heritage objects; state cadastre of highways; state cadastre of railways; state cadastre of communication objects; state cadastre of energy facilities; state cadastre of waste disposal and disposal sites; the state cadastre (department of hazardous geological processes), cartography-geodesy,

and state cadastres of areas with high natural risk are assigned to responsible state bodies.

Based on the data of state cadastres, the layers of the geographic information system are created, and this information base serves to obtain the necessary information for legal entities and individuals for ministries, state committees, local authorities, tax authorities. State land cadastre information is particularly important here [1,2].

METHODOLOGY

Methodology of Creation and Management of State Cadastres in the Republic of Uzbekistan is a studied system for collecting, storing and managing land data. This methodology works to ensure consistency and stability of the land management system, regulate legal relations on land, and manage financial accounts. Methodology of Creation and Management of State Cadastres is implemented based on the following processes:

Collection of Land Information: First of all, information about all the land in the country is collected. This information is provided by land name, size, attractions, owner, etc.

Land Data Analysis: Collected data is analyzed and checked for compatibility with cataloging. At this stage, necessary actions can be taken to identify data that is unclear or erroneous.

Financial Accounting: State cadastres are an important tool for financial accounting of land. In this process, land taxes, payments, financial transactions and other financial information are collected [3,4].

Study of Legal Relations: Determining the owner of the land, understanding and regulating the legal relations between the governing bodies are part of the methodology. In this process, local legal relations, permits, etc. are introduced.

Verification and Analysis: All collected data is verified and analyzed. At this stage, completeness and accuracy of information is ensured.

Data storage and presentation: A system for processing and storing the received data will be established. State cadastres work to provide information for other administrative bodies, including financial institutions, investment companies, and citizens.

The methodology of creation and management of State Cadastres in the Republic of Uzbekistan is aimed at ensuring consistency and stability in the collection, storage and management of land data. This system plays an important

role in land regulation, regulation of legal relations, management of financial accounts, and promotion of investments.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Concept of state cadastre and its content. Networks of state cadastres are a component of the unified system of state cadastres, as well as updated information on the geographical location, legal status, quantity, quality descriptions and price of a certain type of natural, economic object or other object. and will consist of a system of documents.

As a modern definition of the concept of cadastre, it can be said that cadastre is a system of collecting, storing and referring to users information on the current state of natural resources and human-made material and spiritual wealth in the territory of our country [5,6].

Due to the fact that natural and material resources are divided into several types, the system of state cadastres also includes several branch cadastres. For example, land cadastre, cadastre of energy resources, cadastre of animal world, cadastre of railways, cadastre of buildings and structures, cadastre of water resources, forest cadastre, cadastre of architectural monuments and historical monuments, cadastre of communications, etc. The land cadastre has a special place among these cadastres due to the fact that any wealth in the territory of the country is located either underground or above the ground.

Taking into account the development of economic reforms carried out in all sectors of the national economy, rational use of natural and economic resources and improvement of the management system for their protection, comprehensive analysis and assessment of the natural and economic potential of the regions is one of the most necessary issues.

The cadastral system, which is considered one of the main elements of the market economy, fully complies with the main principles and content of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and today it plays an important role in deepening the reforms in the economic spheres. The content and essence of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Cadastre" adopted by the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 15, 2000 fully defined the principles of creating and maintaining State cadastres in our country.

On the basis of the decision No. 66 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, adopted on February 16, 2005, "On the approval of the Regulation on the procedure for creating and maintaining a unified system of state cadastres" on the creation and maintenance of 21 state network cadastres in our

republic relevant ministries, state committees and agencies are appointed as responsible. The unified system of state cadastres (DKYT) is a multi-purpose information system that combines all types of state cadastres. Its maintenance is entrusted to the cadastral agency [7,8].

The cadastral agency coordinates the activities of ministries, state committees, agencies and local state authorities in the field of state cadastre maintenance and maintains a unified system of state cadastres. The development of the methodology, scientific principles and concepts of the unified system of state cadastres was determined by the interested ministries, state committees and agencies that manage the state cadastre. Today, a complete regulatory legal framework has been formed for the creation and maintenance of state cadastres, and the relevant decisions of our government regulations on the maintenance and creation of state cadastres were approved and put into operation.

Currently, state cadastres; state cadastre of land, mines, minerals and man-made derivatives; state water cadastre; state forest cadastre; state cadastre of protected natural areas; state cadastre of buildings and structures; state cadastre of hydrotechnical facilities; state cadastre of cultural heritage objects; state cadastre of highways; state cadastre of railways; state cadastre of communication objects; state cadastre of energy facilities; state cadastre of waste disposal and disposal sites; State cadastre of high natural risk zones (department of dangerous geological processes), cartography-geodesy state cadastre, data in the form of a thematic layer is entered into the central database of the Unified State Cadastre System (DKYT).

Today, the layers of the geographic information system are being created based on the information of the State Cadastre. State land cadastre information is particularly important here. The main purpose of maintaining the state land cadastre is to establish the legal basis for the use of cadastral data for the development of the economy, the provision of guarantees of rights to land plots, the rational use of land, and their protection. Cadastral documents are being prepared for land plots located in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and Tashkent city, and the rights of legal and natural persons to land plots are being registered with the state register. based on the approved decisions, the land report is prepared and presented to the cadastral agency in the region as of January 1 at the end of each year [9,10].

At present, the rights of legal entities and individuals to the land plot are registered by the state, and the information in the process of registration is sent to the official e-mail of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions (districts and cities) and the city of Tashkent. being included in the maps. Today, all district, city land surveying and real estate cadastral services have 160 state-of-the-art geodetic

equipment with complete satellite system in order to carry out quick and accurate measurement of agricultural crops and improve the quality of topogeodetic work. appropriate software, modern computers, and in order to introduce a unified software system, regional offices and district departments are provided with ArcGIS software.

State land cadastre information After the state registration of rights to land plots belonging to each legal entity and natural person in districts and cities in the prescribed manner, a database is created on the spot and a unified system of state cadastres in the form of a table in the coordinate system being entered into the database. In accordance with the decisions made by our government in recent years, work is currently underway to create a single computerized national system of state registration of rights to real estate. In the future, it is planned to create a single data bank containing attributive and graphical information about real estate.

In order to prepare a cadastral summary file for real estate objects, legal entities and individuals can submit their applications in the form of an electronic document to the Land Resources of the Republic of Uzbekistan using electronic digital signatures through telecommunication channels of their choice. It is planned to send geodesy, cartography and state cadastre in electronic form through a single portal and information resource of the State Committee of Interactive State Services [11].

In this direction, the system of electronic reception and processing of the application and the documents attached to it is a complex of information systems, as well as communication channels and software - hardware tools that ensure the information security of information transmission and reception, processing of received information, software for its storage. -hardware programs are being developed.

In accordance with the "Regulation on the procedure for state registration of rights to real estate and transactions concluded on it" approved by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 1 dated January 7, 2014, on the rights of legal entities and individuals to land plots, buildings and structures (including underground structures), perennial trees, as well as mortgages and mortgages of material rights to buildings and structures and land plots the state registration procedure is being introduced on the basis of the "one window" principle, using contracts and information and communication technologies.

In accordance with the government's decision, the "State Investment Program" is currently being implemented by the cadastral agency, taking into account the experience of leading foreign countries, to create a computerized unified national system of state registration of rights to real estate.

In the future, it is planned to create a single data bank containing attributive and graphical information about real estate.

Procedure for maintaining state cadastres. Management of state cadastres is carried out by relevant ministries, state committees, agencies and local state authorities. The maintenance of state cadastres includes the following: transfer of property rights and other rights to cadastral objects from the state register; taking into account the quantitative and qualitative descriptions of cadastral objects; assessment of cadastral objects in terms of quality and value; Systematization, storage and updating of cadastral information; making reports on the state of cadastral objects; Providing relevant information for inclusion in the unified system of state cadastres; providing users with cadastre information in the manner prescribed by law [12].

The owners of the cadastral objects and the owners of other rights to the cadastral objects to the relevant ministries, state committees, agencies, local government authorities about the geographical location, legal status, quantity, quality descriptions and prices of the cadastral objects, they must also provide information about current changes in their status. The procedure for maintaining state cadastres is approved by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Financing of state cadastre management is carried out at the expense of the state budget.

State registration of rights to cadastral objects. State registration of rights to cadastral objects is a legal document of state recognition and confirmation of the rights of legal entities and individuals to cadastral objects. State registration of rights to cadastral objects is carried out by entering information confirmed by documents into state registers. State registration of rights to cadastral objects is mandatory for all owners of cadastral objects and owners of other rights to cadastral objects.

Accounting of cadastral objects. Accounting of cadastral objects is carried out by relevant departments of ministries, state committees, agencies, local government bodies within the boundaries of cadastral objects, as well as settlements, districts, regions, natural and economic regions, and the entire Republic of Uzbekistan. according to their actual status and their use.

Assessment of cadastral objects. Assessment of cadastral objects includes assessment in terms of quality and value. Qualitative assessment of cadastral objects is carried out on the basis of their natural and physical characteristics. Valuation of cadastral objects in terms of value is carried out in accordance with the procedure established by law, taking into account their specific characteristics.

Cadastral documents. Documents confirming ownership and other rights to the cadastral object, cadastral collection of the object, cadastral map (plan), cadastral book, report on the condition of cadastral objects are the main types of cadastral documents [13].

Cadastre collection - cadastral photographing, technical inventory and passporting of the cadastral object necessary for the formation, accounting and subsequent state registration of the right to the cadastral object, special inspection and research, will consist of documents, materials and information of the assessment in terms of quality and value.

A cadastral map (plan) is a graphic drawing document that shows the land where cadastral objects are located, their borders, protection tags, assessment, quantity and quality descriptions, and it is made on paper, magnetic and other means.

The cadastral book is considered the main document for registration and accounting of cadastral objects, it consists of information about the geographical location, legal status, quantitative and qualitative descriptions and evaluation of cadastral objects.

The report on the state of cadastral objects is prepared according to the established procedure for each type of state cadastre and includes information on the quantity and quality of cadastral objects in individual regions and the entire Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as their value includes [14].

CONCLUSION

The system of creation and maintenance of state cadastres in the Republic of Uzbekistan is managed by the land office of the country. This system integrates information about land in the country and makes it available to other authorities for the management and distribution of information. The state cadastre deals with issues of collection, storage and presentation of information about land. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is of great importance to create and maintain state cadastres, to collect, store and manage information about land in the country. These systems are important tools for the country in land regulation, defining legal relations, increasing investments and managing financial transactions.

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